

1 **Mobilization of the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) program in schizophrenia.**

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7 We studied induced pluripotent stem cell models and primary tissues from the brains of humans with
8 schizophrenia. We identified changes in collagen expression in genes *Col1a1* and *Col1a2* consistent with
9 EMT program activity. Accordingly, EMT program regulators from the SNAI family including *SNAI1* and
10 *SNAI3* were among the genes most differentially expressed in diseased iPS cells or in cells from the
11 schizophrenic brain. EMT program changes in schizophrenia may be a model for a wider occurrence in
12 chronic human disease, or epithelial-mesenchymal transition changes may be a specifically important
13 aspect of the schizophrenia disease gene expression program.
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